

IMPACT DAMAGE AND PERFORATION OF THIN MONOLITHIC ALUMINIUM ALLOY PLATES: INSIGHTS FOR IMPACT RESISTANT POLYMER-METAL BI-LAYER LAMINATES

Kedar S. Pandya¹, Graham J. McShane¹ and William J. Stronge¹

¹Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge
Trumpington Street, Cambridge CB2 1PZ, UK
Email: kp415@cam.ac.uk

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ABSTRACT

Resistance to impact damage is an essential requirement of several light-weight structural components. Quasi-static and impact experiments performed by Mohagheghian [1] have shown that polymer-metal bi-layer laminates are able to achieve a higher impact perforation resistance than either monolithic polymer or monolithic metal plates of the same mass. The polymer and metal layers interact in a synergistic manner, the polymer layer deforming under the projectile, altering its effective tip geometry and hence the mode of deformation and fracture of the metallic substrate. In order to investigate this mechanism and identify optimal configurations, numerical models are required. A key challenge is to develop a model for the metallic substrate that is able to reproduce the correct sensitivity to the state of stress induced by impacting projectiles of highly variable effective tip geometry. This is the focus of the present investigation. We first consider experimentally the perforation of light-weight aluminium alloy plates struck by rigid projectiles with a variety of nose shapes, to evaluate the sensitivity of the target to different states of stress. Next, we consider the finite element modelling of the impact response of the aluminium alloy plates. The quasi-static model in [1] is modified to account for dynamic effects, including a consideration of the appropriate failure criterion. Here we consider the modified Mohr-Coulomb (MMC) fracture surface [2] for ductile metals, and strategies to calibrate and validate it for high strain rate loading, in order to best predict the ballistic impact behaviour. Modes of deformation, damage and failure during ballistic impact are assessed experimentally. Four distinct stages of penetration / perforation are observed in the numerical predictions; initial damage, complete damage, lower ballistic limit and upper ballistic limit. This study has important implications for better understanding the ballistic impact behaviour of polymer-metal bi-layer targets.

1 INTRODUCTION

Quasi-static and impact experiments performed by Mohagheghian [1] have shown that polymer-metal bi-layer laminates are able to achieve a higher impact perforation resistance than either monolithic polymer or monolithic metal plates of the same mass. The polymer and metal layers interact in a synergistic manner, the polymer layer deforming under the projectile, altering its effective tip geometry and hence the mode of deformation and fracture of the metallic substrate. In order to investigate this mechanism and identify optimal configurations, numerical models are required. A key challenge is to develop a model for the metallic substrate that is able to reproduce the correct sensitivity to the state of stress induced by impacting projectiles of highly variable effective tip geometry. The present investigation focuses on numerical and experimental studies on the impact response of thin aluminium alloy plates. Impact and perforation behaviour, ballistic limit velocity, energy absorption capability and sensitivity to projectile nose shape are evaluated. This study serves to inform model development, suitable to capture the necessary stress state sensitivity. The present work bridges the gap between the quasi-static perforation response of thin metallic plates obtained by [1] for a range of projectile nose shapes and the higher strain rate impact behaviour.

2 FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATIONS

In order to predict ductile fracture over a wide range of stress states, the MMC model [2] is used, which takes into account the effect of hydrostatic stress and Lode angle on ductile fracture. In the present study, aluminium alloy AA 6082 T4 of 1 mm thickness was selected. Due to its relatively high ductility, the sensitivity of fracture of AA 6082 T4 to material defects is low. As a result, calibration results of the ductile fracture model are reliable [1].

Mohagheghian [1] considered the effects of anisotropy of the aluminium sheets, and accounted for it by performing tensile tests on dog-bone specimens machined with orientations parallel, perpendicular and at 45° to the rolling direction.

The post-necking strain hardening behaviour was assumed to follow power law relationship at large plastic strains given by:

$$\bar{\sigma} = A(\varepsilon_0 + \bar{\varepsilon}_p)^n \quad (1)$$

where, $\bar{\sigma}$ and $\bar{\varepsilon}_p$ denote equivalent stress and equivalent plastic strain, respectively. A , ε_0 and n are coefficients obtained by fitting the power law relationship with experimental data, the values of which are presented in Table 1 [1].

A	n	ε_0
480	0.0027	0.19

Table 1: Coefficients of power law isotropic hardening for AA 6082 T4 [1].

In the MMC model proposed by Bai & Wierzbicki [2], the onset of failure is taken to occur when the damage indicator D (defined in [2]) becomes equal to 1. By excluding the dependence of the hardening rule on hydrostatic pressure and Lode angle proposed by Bai & Wierzbicki [2], the MMC model reduces to:

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_f = \left\{ \frac{A}{c_2} \times \left[\sqrt{\frac{1+c_1^2}{3}} \cos\left(\frac{\bar{\theta}\pi}{6}\right) + c_1 \left(\eta + \frac{1}{3} \sin\left(\frac{\bar{\theta}\pi}{6}\right) \right) \right] \right\}^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad (2)$$

where, $\bar{\varepsilon}_f$ is the effective plastic strain at the point of fracture, η is stress triaxiality and $\bar{\theta}$ is the normalised Lode angle. c_1 and c_2 are calibration parameters obtained from experimental data and numerical simulations. Since η and $\bar{\theta}$ are not constant during deformation in several loading cases, average values of stress triaxiality, η_{avg} and normalised Lode angle, $\bar{\theta}_{avg}$ over the equivalent plastic strain range up to the point of fracture are used for calibration [3, 4].

Mohagheghian [1] performed two types of characterisation experiments to obtain effective plastic strain at fracture under two different states of stress; tensile tests on dog-bone specimens and notched specimens. A combined experimental and numerical method was used to evaluate the calibration constants for modelling ductile fracture considering effects of mesh sensitivity and metal anisotropy on post-necking and failure mode. The fracture conditions for dog-bone and notched specimens are presented in Table 2.

Test	$\bar{\varepsilon}_f$	η_{avg}	$\bar{\theta}_{avg}$
Tensile (dog-bone)	0.63	0.398	0.856
Tensile (notched)	0.50	0.507	0.451

Table 2: Fracture conditions for dog-bone and notched specimens [1].

The effect of boundary conditions, anisotropy and friction on the indentation response of clamped plates was simulated using a 3D FE quarter plate model in Abaqus/Standard perforated with a hemispherical indenter [1]. This was in turn used to develop and validate an equivalent 2D axisymmetric model, allowing greater resolution of the impact point at lower numerical cost. In the present study, an identical axisymmetric model is used for the impact simulations, implemented in

Abaqus/Explicit V6.13. Axisymmetric continuum elements (CAX4R) were used to discretise the aluminium plate and the projectile was modelled using rigid elements (RAX2). The majority of the plate was meshed with four elements through the thickness. Local mesh refinement under the projectile was carried out for each projectile nose shape.

Plate fracture was modelled by implementing the MMC damage criterion, and failure was considered to occur when failure initiation ($D = 1$) took place at any location in the model. The MMC failure locus was implemented in Abaqus in tabular form. Element deletion after failure was implemented. Each impact case was simulated at least three times to ensure stability of the result. It should be noted that damage in the target plate was restricted to ring cracking in the axisymmetric model. Other tensile failure modes such as radial cracking and petal formation and bending were not captured.

Impact characteristics of the metal target plate were obtained by varying the incident velocity of the projectile, measuring its residual velocity and hence obtaining the energy absorbed by the target. Deformation and damage behaviour during ballistic impact was also noted.

3 EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

The test specimens used in the present study consist of flat monolithic aluminium alloy plates (AA 6082 T4) of thickness $h = 1$ mm with a circular target area of radius $R = 50$ mm fully clamped around the edge (Figure 1a). The boundary condition is provided by a circular steel clamping ring with inner diameter 100 mm. Twelve M4 bolts are used to fasten the clamping ring through clearance holes in the test specimen (a square plate of side length 130 mm) to a supporting plate.

Projectiles with diameter $d_p = 12.5$ mm and mass $m_p = 20.2 \pm 0.2$ g were machined from mild steel. Ballistic impact experiments with different projectile nose shapes were carried out. The nose shape of the projectile was changed from blunt to hemi-spherical in two ways, either by introducing different corner radii (R_c) or by changing the frontal nose radii (R_f). Note that the limiting cases $R_c = 1 / R_f = 0$ correspond to a blunt tip, and $R_c = R_f = d_p/2$ a hemi-spherical tip. These two series of tip geometries provided a wide range of loading conditions, deformation modes and failure mechanisms. It should be mentioned that despite the difference in nose shape all projectiles were designed to have the same mass. No plastic deformation of the projectile was observed during any of the impact experiments.

Figure 1: Schematic of target plate clamping arrangement for impact testing.

The projectile was fired using a single stage gas gun with a barrel of internal diameter 12.7 mm. The specimen supporting plate was mounted to a steel frame and oriented normal to the barrel, so that the projectile impacted at 90° to the target. A high speed camera (Vision Research Phantom V710) oriented perpendicular to the flight of the projectile was used to record the motion of the projectile during its interaction with the target. The projectile was designed with a tail of diameter 5 mm and length 20 mm, in which reference grooves were machined, so that the high speed camera could continue to track the projectile motion throughout its interaction with the target, even when the nose was obscured by the clamping frame. The high speed images therefore provided measurements of both the impact velocity V_i and the residual velocity V_r . Positive velocity was defined in the direction of initial impact. Negative V_r therefore indicates reflection of the projectile, and a positive V_r indicates perforation. Laser velocity gauges mounted at the barrel exit were used to verify the impact velocity obtained from the high speed photography, and showed good agreement.

A measure of the ballistic limit for each projectile nose shape was obtained by plotting V_r against V_i for a number of impact experiments. A curve was fitted through all data points with $V_r > 0$. The intersection of this curve with the residual velocity axis is considered to be the upper ballistic limit. Similarly, a curve was fitted through all data points with $V_r < 0$. The intersection of this curve with the residual velocity axis is considered to be the lower ballistic limit. The energy absorbed, E_A is calculated as:

$$E_A = \frac{1}{2} m_p (V_i^2 - V_r^2) \quad (3)$$

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Ballistic limit and energy absorption capability

Ballistic impact response of thin aluminium alloy plates is investigated both numerically and experimentally in terms of ballistic limit and energy absorption capability. In order to assess the effect of state of stress on ductile fracture during ballistic impact, numerical predictions of two types of failure models are presented; the MMC model which takes into account the effect of stress triaxiality and Lode angle, and a simpler constant failure strain criteria with a value of effective failure strain equal to 0.63 independent of stress state (obtained from tensile tests on dog-bone specimens [1]).

Figures 2a and 2b show numerical predictions of energy absorbed, E_A during ballistic impact perforation using MMC failure model for projectiles with different corner and frontal nose radii respectively. Numerical predictions of energy absorbed, E_A during ballistic impact perforation using constant failure strain model for projectiles with different corner and frontal nose radii are given in Figures 3a and 3b respectively for comparison.

As shown in Figures 2 and 3, four distinct stages of penetration / perforation are observed in the numerical predictions. Initial damage is considered to take place at the minimum incident projectile velocity for which the damage indicator D equals unity (MMC failure model) or the effective failure strain reaches a value of 0.63 (constant failure strain model). A ring crack is initiated under the projectile at this stage. This crack gradually propagates towards the back face of the target. Complete damage is assumed to take place at the minimum incident projectile velocity for which the ring crack formed spans the thickness of the target. At higher incident projectile velocities, perforation of the thin metal target takes place. The minimum incident projectile velocity at which the projectile residual velocity is zero is defined as the lower ballistic limit. Similarly, the maximum incident projectile velocity for which the projectile residual velocity is zero is denoted the upper ballistic limit. These limits span the range of incident velocities for which the projectile is arrested by the target plate.

Based on Figures 2 and 3, it is observed that the energy absorbed by the metal target for all four stages of penetration / perforation is significantly influenced by the nose shape of the projectile. In the case of both variation in R_c and R_f , the energy absorbed by the target at the ballistic limit (both upper and lower) is maximum for a projectile nose shape that is intermediate between blunt and hemispherical.

Figure 2: Numerical predictions of energy absorbed, E_A during ballistic impact perforation using MMC failure model for projectiles with (a) different corner radii, R_c and (b) different frontal nose radii, R_f .

Figure 3: Numerical predictions of energy absorbed, E_A during ballistic impact perforation using constant failure strain model for projectiles with (a) different corner radii, R_c and (b) different frontal nose radii, R_f .

It is interesting to note the sharper peak in energy absorption when varying R_f compared to R_c , irrespective of the failure model used. In the present study, the global maximum energy absorbed by the metal target is for the case of a projectile with $R_f = 9$ mm (Figures 2b and 3b). This significantly exceeds the energy absorbed by the target when impacted by either a hemi-spherical or blunt projectile. An objective for resilient polymer-metal bi-layer laminate design is therefore to achieve this state of stress in the metallic substrate layer.

Some differences are noted between the predictions of the two failure models. The MMC failure model (Figure 2a) predicts a steady decrease in the ballistic limit range (BLR), defined as the difference in E_A between the upper and lower ballistic limits, with the transition from blunt to hemispherical projectile. This corresponds to a shift in the dominant failure mechanism from shear plugging in case of a blunt projectile to predominantly tensile failure for a hemispherical projectile. A similar trend is observed for variations in both R_c and R_f (Figure 2b). In contrast, the constant failure strain model does not display this trend. The constant failure strain model also consistently predicts a higher E_A compared to the MMC failure model for the different projectile nose shapes considered in the present study (Figures 2 and 3). This can be explained by the fact that the MMC model results in a lower effective failure strain for the relevant stress states.

A comparison between experimental results and numerical values based on the MMC failure model is shown in Figures 4a and 4b. It may be noted that only the lower and upper ballistic limits can be obtained experimentally. Ductile fracture is a local phenomenon occurring by nucleation, growth and coalescence of micro-voids leading to macroscopic cracks. Thus it is difficult to experimentally determine the incident projectile velocities corresponding to initial and complete damage within the target plate.

Figure 4: Comparison between experimental and numerical values of E_A (based on the MMC failure model) for projectiles with (a) different corner radii, R_c and (b) different frontal nose radii, R_f .

Experimental data on the energy absorbed during ballistic impact of metal plates shows a similar trend to the results of the numerical simulations. However, the predicted values of E_A are not in good agreement with the experiments. These results are in contradiction to the quasi-static punch indentation results obtained by [1], which show excellent agreement in both the trends and magnitude of E_A . This indicates two issues that might be addressed, to improve the quality of the impact predictions. First, the importance of strain rate dependent plasticity must be considered, although the strain rate sensitivity of this alloy is modest at these loading rates. Secondly, the strain rate dependence of the MMC failure surface needs to be investigated. At present, this is calibrated under quasi-static loading conditions. Strain rate may alter the underlying damage mechanisms, and hence the position and shape of the failure surface in stress space.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Numerical and experimental investigation on the impact response of thin aluminium alloy plates is presented. Impact damage and perforation behaviour, ballistic limit velocity, energy absorption capability and sensitivity to projectile nose shape are evaluated. Modes of deformation, damage and failure during ballistic impact are assessed experimentally. The specific observations are:

- Four distinct stages of penetration / perforation are observed in the numerical predictions; initial damage, complete damage, lower ballistic limit and upper ballistic limit.
- Energy absorbed by the metal target is significantly influenced by the nose shape of the projectile. It is highest for a projectile nose shape intermediate between blunt and hemispherical. There exists an optimum projectile nose shape for which energy absorption by the target is maximised.
- A sharper peak in energy absorbed by the target is obtained by varying the projectile tip radius R_f , versus the corner radius R_c . The global maximum in energy absorbed by the target is for the case $R_f = 9$ mm.
- In the present study, the MMC failure surface is calibrated under quasi-static loading. There is a need to recalibrate the MMC failure surface at high strain rates in order to better predict the ballistic impact behaviour.

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